

THE CONCEPT OF QUALITY OF LIFE AND FOREIGN RESEARCH EXPERIENCE QUALITY OF LIFE OF THE POPULATION

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Annotation. The relevance of the research topic lies in the fact that society is constantly evolving, which leads to an increase in needs and the study of the main trends in improving the quality of life to maximize their satisfaction is the main indicator of the effectiveness of regional authorities.

The quality of life of the population is a comprehensive assessment of the level and conditions of people's lives, reflecting the subjective perception of life and its individual aspects, as well as the degree and ability to meet social, material, and spiritual needs, is the most important social category, since it characterizes the structure of human needs

Keywords: quality of life, life expectancy, income level, economic growth.

Improving the quality of life of the population in all countries is a social task. However, the solution to this problem lies both in overcoming the limited budgetary resources of the economies of various countries and in building a universal market economy with a social orientation.

Accordingly, today, in the world, there is no unilateral solution to this problem. At the same time, it is possible to use the diverse experience of developed countries in improving the quality of life of the population.

Since the beginning of the 1990s, the UN has provided a yearly report on the quality of life surveys around the world. It displays the ranking of countries,

the places which are identified by points. The parameters of this rating include life expectancy, development of the health care and education system, social security, ecology, crime rate, respect for human rights, and the size of the gross national income per capita.

An analysis of this rating and, accordingly, the experience of the developed economies of the world in improving the quality of life of the population, shows that the countries with the "Swedish model" significantly exceed the capitalist countries of Western Europe and the USA in these indicators. The countries of the "Swedish model" include countries where active state regulation of the socio-economic sphere is developed.

The main sources of budget and social spending in such countries are rather high taxes levied on a progressive scale.

For example, in the mid-1990s, the public sector in Sweden provided 32% of all services provided in the country, while in the USA they accounted for 14%.

There are other strong differences, in particular, other tools and mechanisms for solving the socio-economic problem in the context of the globalization of markets. These include budgetary and social and financial policy, flexible changes in legislation, as well as the practice of regulating wages on the basis of collective agreements. And through solving the problem of ensuring stable inflation and full employment of the population in these countries, the problem of poverty is solved, and the quality of life is also improved.

The basis for solving the socio-economic problem was the reduction of taxes for businesses and the monetary policy of demand to zero or near zero inflation. Since, thanks to this, full employment was not observed, additional state regulation measures were implemented through public works, government orders, and stimulation of the activity of entrepreneurs and small businesses.

In addition, improving the quality of life of the population is achieved in these countries through free health care, education, insurance, and social security. Social equalization and inequality were addressed by raising wage rates for low-

paid occupations, as well as raising taxes for high-paying ones.

Despite the fact that many firms were unable to increase the wages of their employees and had to close, the laid-off employees were not left without help. For them, institutions for the training and retraining of personnel, recruitment services, and services for forecasting demanded types of employment were prepared. Even large subsidies for disabled workers were thought out. As a result, people who lost their jobs due to an unprofitable enterprise or business received a new highly paid job.

This practice has given countries with the "Swedish model" more effective results than ordinary assistance to the unemployed through the payment of benefits in most Western countries. It can even be noted that these countries still have some of the most stable and socially oriented economies in the world.

As for other countries, in Spain, for example, the Moncloa Pact was adopted, which also increased the wages of the poorest segments of the population. In Italy, for the differentiation of income, a special settlement program was developed and adopted, associated with a flexible taxation system. Germany introduced a system of various shares to the least protected sections of the population, thanks to which it had significant dividends. In England, a social contract was practiced, where various social conditions for future work were specified in advance.

High life expectancy is considered to be a consequence of the high level of development of the economy, health and medical services, scientific and technological progress, the elimination of inequality, the growth of culture, and the level of education in general.

High life expectancy is the main condition for increasing the efficiency and productivity of labor, increasing the level of education, social equality, and scientific progress in a broad sense.

The growth of life expectancy ensures stable ties between generations,

accumulation, transfer, and better analysis of acquired knowledge, improvement of learning abilities

The main indicator of average life expectancy in the countries of the world is the index of life expectancy. The index is considered a key one in matters of socio-economic development.

Every year, according to the methodology of the UN Development Program, the indicator of life expectancy is calculated. The indicator is calculated on the basis of statistical data provided by national institutions and organizations.

The indicator calculates life expectancy in general, as well as for men and women separately, taking into account the peculiarities of the gender phenomenon

Of course, many factors influence health and life expectancy, including heredity, nature of work, ecology, and socio-economic conditions.

Life expectancy in foreign countries

№	Countries and regions	General	Women	Men
1	Hong Kong	85,29	88,17	82,38
2	Japan	85,03	88,09	81,91
3	Macau	84,68	87,62	81,73
4	Switzerland	84,25	86,02	82,42
5	Singapore	84,07	86,15	82,06
6	Italy	84,01	85,97	81,90
7	Spain	83,99	86,68	81,27
8	Australia	83,94	85,80	82,02
9	channel islands	83,60	85,31	81,82
10	Iceland	83,52	84,90	82,15
11	Korea	83,50	86,42	80,46
12	Israel	83,49	84,91	81,98

13	Sweden	83,33	84,97	81,69
14	France	83,13	85,82	80,32
15	Malta	83,06	84,68	81,37
16	Canada	82,96	84,74	81,15
17	Norway	82,94	84,78	81,11
18	Ireland	82,81	84,32	81,29
19	Greece	82,80	85,08	80,52
20	New Zealand	82,79	84,38	81,20
106	Russia	72,99	78,15	67,62
<p>Source: United Nations [Electronic resource]: Population department report 2019 and 2020</p> <p>– Access mode: https://www.un.org/ru/sections/issues-depth/population/index.html (date of the application : 31.03.2021)</p>				

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Today, the health and life expectancy of the population is becoming part of human capital. In this case, a person, depending on the level of education, can invest in quality rest, sports, and quality nutrition, or independently destroy their health. The question is whether the income level of the population is sufficient to ensure the demand for this type of service, including health care services.

Depending on the welfare and level of development of countries, factors affecting the quality and life expectancy, the mortality rate varies significantly. The key factors for low life expectancy in developing countries are considered to be: low income, high crime rates, poor food quality and

malnutrition, poor sanitary and epidemiological conditions, and housing. While in developed countries life expectancy is affected by: excessive alcohol consumption, physical inactivity, high-stress levels, and obesity and its consequences.

To be sure, life expectancy in high-income countries is substantially higher than in developing or third-world countries. According to statistics, in 2017, the life expectancy of the population of developed countries was 82 years, while in countries with economies in transition - 69. At the same time, it was noted that the increase in income levels, health care, and the general quality of life in developing countries have a greater effect on life expectancy than in developed ones. This is explained by the fact that it is easier to increase life expectancy from 50 to 60 or 70 years than from 80 to 90. Thus, the significance of the experience of developed countries in improving the quality of life of the population lies in the fact that a high quality of life is ensured not for one percent of citizens, but for all segments of the population, thanks to the equal right to vote for all in the distribution of public goods, where the state itself is the regulator.

Of course, there is a downside, when government intervention, counteracting the negative aspects of the market, can itself resist it. However, this is precisely why the international experience of the functioning of market economies with a "human face", stabilizing rather than undermining state integrity and stability, is very necessary for the economic development of Russia.

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